

from aqueous dioxan (9 : 1) gave yellow micro needles, m.p. 276° (decomp.).

The I.R. spectrum of the (II) showed the characteristic bands at 1650 (Carbonyl), 1580 (Aromatic), 30 0-3360 (NH) and 1530 cm⁻¹ (Nitro).

(Found C, 32.91% ; H, 2.15% ; N, 14.08% ; C₂₈H₃₄O₄N₃Br requires C, 33.11% ; H, 2.75% ; N, 14.48%).

Hydrazones of estrone—

(i) *With 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromobenzohydrazide (I)*: 2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo-benzohydrazide (0.2 gm.) was dissolved in methanol (12 ml.). Estrone (0.2 gm. dissolved in 25 ml. of methanol) and acetic acid (0.2 ml.) were added to it and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 mins and then concentrated by removing methanol under reduced pressure. It was cooled in ice and diluted with cold water. A bulky white precipitate appeared after some time which was filtered, washed with a small quantity of aqueous methanol and dried. Yield 62%. It was crystallised from methanol when colourless micro needles were obtained, m.p. 196°.

(Found C, 57.63% ; H, 4.91% ; N, 4.84% ; C₂₈H₃₄O₃N₂ClBr requires C, 57.96% ; H, 5.02% ; N, 5.41%)

(ii) *With 2-methoxy-3-nitro-5-bromobenzohydrazide (II)*: 2-Methoxy-3-nitro-5-bromobenzohydrazide (0.2 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 ml.). Estrone (0.2 gm. dissolved in 30 ml. of absolute alcohol) was added to it. To the reaction mixture glacial acetic acid (0.2 ml.) was added and the reaction was carried out further as described above. Yield 75%. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol, when light yellow colour needles were obtained, m.p. 234° (decomp.).

(Found C, 57.18% ; H, 4.82% ; N, 7.12% ; C₂₈H₃₄O₃N₃Br requires C, 57.57% ; H, 5.16% ; N, 7.75%.)

Hydrazones of dehydro-epiandrosterone—

(i) *With 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromobenzohydrazide (I)*. The preparation was carried out as described in the case of estrone.

Yield 50%. Colourless needles, m.p. 166°.

(Found C, 57.82% ; H, 6.25% ; N, 4.90% ; C₂₈H₃₄O₃N₂ClBr requires C, 58.27% ; H, 5.97% ; N, 5.22%.)

(ii) *With 2-methoxy-3-nitro-5-bromobenzohydrazide (II)*. The procedure was same as in the case of estrone. Yield 45%. Yellow colour micro needles, m.p. 150°.

Found C, 57.21% ; H, 5.91% ; N, 6.82% ; C₂₉H₃₄O₃N₃Br requires C, 57.86% ; H, 6.07% ; N, 7.50%)

Hydrazones of 5-β-androsterone—

(i) *With 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromobenzohydrazide (I)* The preparation was carried out as described in the case of estrone.

Yield was found to be 60%, colourless needles, m.p. 110°.

(Found C, 57.82% ; H, 6.25% ; N, 5.29% ; C₂₈H₃₄O₃N₂BrCl requires C, 58.03% ; H, 6.32% ; N, 5.21%.)

(ii) *With 2-methoxy-3-nitro-5-bromobenzohydrazide (II)*. The procedure was same as in the case of estrone.

Yield 40%. Yellow colour micro needles, m.p. 210° (decomp.).

(Found C, 57.95% ; H, 6.02% ; N, 8.21% ; C₂₇H₃₄O₃N₃Br requires C, 57.66% ; H, 6.40% ; N, 7.47%.)

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